

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

NEW PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING VOCABULARY

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Abstract

The vocabulary helps understand concepts and think more coherently. The more words a youngster has, the better he or she will be able to comprehend and communicate concepts to others. It improves a child's persuasion skills. A large vocabulary will enable a youngster to speak in a more interesting manner. There are certain principles in vocabulary teaching that can help teachers: to determine the terminology that students require; allow for the acquisition of language through accidental learning; numerous engagement in multimodal and multi-sensorial ways; ensure implicit instruction is accompanied by explicit instruction; examine vocabulary in a range of genres by using a variety of text forms; use Word Families to expand vocabulary; make multiple meaningful contacts with target words; and so on. Also, we examined two strategies for acquiring vocabulary: increasing vocabulary learning opportunities and improving word learning capabilities. We have investigated some techniques for remembering words. Those techniques are more suitable for children. We also clarified various activities based on teaching vocabulary.

Keywords: vocabulary, strategy, teaching, learning, lexis

The term "vocabulary" refers to a group of words rather than a single word. Recent vocabulary research is based on an understanding of lexis, the Greek term for "all the words in a language, the full vocabulary of a language," which in English "refers to all the words in a language, the entire vocabulary of a language" (Barcroft, Sunderman, & Schmitt, 2011, p. 571) [3; 571]. So it should come as no surprise that lexical chunks, or phrases of two or more words, such as Good morning and Nice to meet you, are also included in vocabulary. According to studies, infants and adults acquire lexical chunks as single lexical units. These phrases contain more than one word yet have a consistent, formulaic usage and account for a considerable amount of spoken and written English usage. They are also known as formulaic sequences (Alali & Schmitt, 2012) [1; 148], and they are crucial to English vocabulary development, so teachers should pay attention to them while teaching vocabulary (Lewis, 1993) [23; 76].

Thus, vocabulary may be described as a language's words, including single items, phrases, or chunks of many words that convey a certain meaning in the same manner as individual words do. Single lexical items - words with distinct meanings - are addressed by vocabulary, but it also includes lexical phrases or chunks.

Teaching vocabulary aids pupils in comprehending and communicating in English. The notion of a word may be defined in a variety of ways, but form, meaning, and use are three important components that instructors should be aware of and focus on. The form of a word, according to Nation (2001) includes its sound (spoken form), spelling (written form), and any word elements that make up this specific item (such as a prefix, root, and suffix). The term uncommunicative is a good example of word components since the prefix un- signifies negative or opposing, communicate is the main word, and -ive is a suffix that means someone or something can accomplish something. They are all used

here to refer to someone or anything who is unable to communicate, therefore uncommunicative.

Nation (2001) defined meaning as "the interaction of form and meaning," or "the notion and the stuff it refers to, as well as the connections that spring to mind when individuals think about a certain term or expression." According to Nation, usage includes the grammatical functions of the word or phrase, common collocations, and any restrictions on its use, such as frequency, level, and so on.

When teachers teach vocabulary to help students learn words and phrases, they can help them acquire any or all of the many components, which will help them improve their English vocabulary understanding and usage.

There are certain guiding principles in vocabulary teaching that can help teachers make educated decisions in the classroom about how to best satisfy their students' vocabulary learning goals.

Principle 1: To determine the terminology that students require

This is what it means to start with the goal in mind. What would your students eventually require before you even started teaching? Adult learners preparing to enter the workforce do not have the same language demands as young children learning to speak. The curriculum might successfully equip students with the requisite word repertoire by defining clear objectives for explicit vocabulary education.

Principle 2: Not all words are created equal. Prioritizing high-frequency terms

For language learners, certain terms are more valuable than others. During the early stages of learning, concentrate on high-frequency words, which are words with a high usefulness and appear often in daily usage. Learners can utilize K1, K2, and K3 vocabulary lists to help them comprehend and use the new language. For example, the word stroll is a high-frequency word that

may be used to communicate a range of meanings when combined with other high-frequency words. As a result, 'walk' should be taught first, followed by 'stroll' (slow and pleasant walking) and 'plod' (slow and difficult walking).

Students can gradually learn mid and low frequency words after learning high frequency words, as these words appear more frequently in real publications such as unabridged novels, newspapers, news broadcasts, magazines, and academic literature.

Principle 3: Words are not utilized by themselves. Collocations can be used to teach vocabulary and help students make connections.

Words frequently travel in groups to express entire meaning. The teaching of word collocations is an essential part of vocabulary instruction. This can assist students in not just learning particular words, but also in efficiently communicating more comprehensive and complicated thoughts. It also extends from a single word to many related words or phrases, allowing for a more efficient rise in vocabulary capacity. Include the collocation 'hit/miss the target' while teaching the term target, for example. On the other hand, expanding vocabulary is as simple as connecting the term with similar ones. Teachers can, for example, associate the term 'target' with its synonyms 'goal' and 'objective.' Teachers should encourage students to investigate the terms in their collocations and connections with other words while teaching these words.

Principle 4: To multiple meaningful contacts with target words

For most second language learners, mastering vocabulary may be difficult. To begin, learning a new word entails being familiar with its form, function, and communication purpose. As a result, knowing it only once may not be enough to help you remember the term. A more effective vocabulary learning outcome may be achieved by providing students with rich examples and readings that incorporate the target term, as well as repeated opportunities to investigate the word's application independently. For example, in addition to selecting books that contain the term that is repeated several times, the teacher can use the word intentionally in the classroom in a variety of ways, such as teacher speak and visual input, to increase learning.

Principle 5: Examining vocabulary in a range of genres by using a variety of text forms

Students will be able to recognize language that is typically used with different text kinds such as procedures, informative texts, and persuasive texts through a range of text types. This method allows students to learn vocabulary in a variety of situations and with various sorts of texts, guaranteeing that they not only develop their vocabulary but are also exposed to actual text genres (recipes, advertising, newspapers, etc.) that have their own distinctive vocabulary. Additionally, pupils will be able to connect with new terminology when investigating language in the actual world as a result of this.

Principle 6: Using Word Families to expand vocabulary

You and your family have something in common, whether you like them or not. Vocabulary is no exception. Word families are collections of words that follow a pattern that allows them to be quickly recognized (can + identify). Prefixes and suffixes are the most common ones to be aware of. Although it may appear incredible (cannot + believe), the significance of word families is not surprising (unsurprising). Look up a word's word family the next time you learn a new term or just want to see how versatile a word you already know is.

Principle 7: Numerous engagement in multi-modal and multi-sensorial way

This idea draws on a variety of intelligence theories. The Internet provides a wealth of resources for users to read, listen to, and interact with textual, visual, and audio information. The Internet can give a wealth of useful, fascinating, and accurate information. In today's environment, a variety of technology may present children with a variety of games to help them acquire language. Some software can assist students in learning vocabulary by providing sensory input in the form of video, sound, and images. The Internet may give children with a wealth of real vocabulary-building material, such as news and social media comments. Students might also benefit from online engagement with others. Traditional games like word puzzles and charades, which are popular during "family time," are fascinating and interesting methods to engage learners outside of the classroom. These materials and technologies can help children improve their vocabulary development.

Principle 8: To implicit instruction is accompanied by explicit instruction

The instructor deconstructs the target words for the pupils independently of context in explicit instruction. This helps pupils to obtain a thorough understanding of the definition and proper usage of the target term. Vocabulary-focused classes are frequently used to teach focusing on a specific word. Mnemonic practice is one of several ways that may be applied.

Guided observing is a method of teaching that may be used to teach explicit vocabulary. Noticing is founded on solid theoretical underpinnings as well (e.g., the noticing hypothesis). Rather of merely listing terms and definitions for kids to memorize, the guided noticing technique helps students to learn by seeing how new vocabulary is used and then making sense of it using contextual cues. Learners can increase their vocabulary size by emphasizing, remembering, and practicing terminology.

Principle 9: Vocabulary instruction must be combined with instruction in the four language skills.

Vocabulary training should be interwoven with the teaching of the four language skills so that a word may be not only comprehended in reading, but also easily identified in hearing, written correctly in writing, and spoken clearly and accurately. Each language skill has a unique input and output reaction, allowing words to be used in a number of ways. When teaching vocabulary, pronunciation, context, spelling, and social connotations must all be taken into account. Students will develop a full understanding of what a word means and how it is used in rich and realistic situations as a result

of this. We should anticipate students to be able to employ newly acquired words for meaningful and purposeful communication in the target language if vocabulary is embedded in this way.

Principle 10: Allowing for the acquisition of language through accidental learning

Vocabulary development can extend beyond the classroom. After class, teachers might encourage and assist students to read widely. Extensive reading not only stimulates kids to study on their own, but it also provides opportunities for accidental vocabulary acquisition while reading in a comfortable setting. Students learn the meanings of new words accidentally and quickly by encountering the same phrases in several relevant circumstances. Teachers might, for example, provide graded reading series appropriate for students' various levels and offer advice on how to keep track of terms learned inadvertently during the reading process. Students who are more advanced can read popular unabridged novels like the Percy Jackson or Harry Potter series.

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